

Distributed Generation and its Social Impact

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ABSTRACT- Distributed generation, defined as generation located at or near the load centres, is being recognised as an environment friendly, reliable, and secure source of power which not only has minimal negative social impacts but also serves to promote social welfare. This paper aims to bring out the salient features of distributed generation from an economic and social perspective. The paper to identify the distributed resources available in India and proposes methods to tap them. It also studies the social consequences of wide spread deployment of distributed systems and their accommodation into the new liberalised energy market of India

I. INTRODUCTION

Most of the electricity produced today is generated in large generating stations, which is then transmitted at high voltage to the load centres and transmitted to consumers at reduced voltage through local distribution systems. In contrast with large generating stations, distributed generation (DG) produce power on a customer's site or at a local distribution network. DG technologies include Engines, Small hydro and gas turbines Fuel cells Photo voltaic systems etc Although they represent a small share of the electricity market they play a key role for applications in which reliability is crucial, as a source of emergency capacity, and as an alternative to expansion of a local network, in developed economies where uninterrupted power supply is essential. In developing countries like India, where the generation is inadequate to meet the demand, reliability and energy security are of lesser importance. Developing country can tap the potential of DG to extend their present generation capacity in an environment friendly and cost friendly manner. The paper is divided into two parts first part examines the various DG technologies and their merits and demerits and the second part studies the social impact of large scale deployment of small, mini and micro projects in India.

II. WHAT IS DISTRIBUTED GENERATION?

Distributed generation, is defined as generation located at or near the load centres [1]. They generate electricity through various small-scale power generation technologies. Distributed energy resources (DER) refers to a variety of small, modular power-generating technologies that can be combined with energy management and storage systems and used to improve the operation of the electricity delivery system, whether or not those technologies are connected to an electricity grid. Projects are generally developed by either the user to avoid the purchase of power from the grid

or an energy service provider who then retails the power to the site.

III. DISTRIBUTED GENERATION TECHNOLOGIES

Commercial energy technologies include:

- IC engines
- Gas turbines
- Micro turbines
- Energy storage technologies

Renewable energy technologies include:

- Fuel cells
- Solar photovoltaic
- Wind & Wave Energy
- Hydro electric energy

Some of them are discussed below:

A. Reciprocating Engines

Reciprocating engines are the most common technology used for distributed generation. They are a proven technology with low capital cost, large size range, fast start-up capability, relatively high electric conversion efficiency (up to 43% for large diesel systems) [1], and good operating reliability. These characteristics, combined with the engines' ability to start up during a power outage, make them the main choice for emergency or standby power supplies. They are by far the most commonly used power generation equipment under 1 MW. The main drawbacks of reciprocating engines are noise, costly maintenance and high emissions, particularly of nitrogen oxides. These emissions can be reduced, with a loss of efficiency, by changing combustion characteristics [1]. Catalytic converters are a proven emissions-control technology. Larger systems can use selective catalytic reduction (SCR) to reduce emissions. Particulate emission control is usually necessary with diesel engines.

B. Gas Turbines

Small industrial gas turbines of 1- 20 MW are commonly used in CHP (combined heat and power) applications. They are particularly useful when higher temperature steam is required than can be produced by a reciprocating engine. The maintenance cost is slightly lower than for reciprocating

engines, but so is the electrical conversion efficiency. Gas turbines can be noisy. Emissions are somewhat lower than for engines, and cost-effective NOx emissions-control technology is commercially available [1].

C. Micro turbines

One of the most striking technical characteristics of micro turbines is their extremely high rotational speed. The turbine rotates up to 120 000 rpm and the generator up to 40 000 rpm. Individual units range from 30-200 kW but can be combined readily into systems of multiple units. Low combustion temperatures can assure very low NOx emissions levels. They make much less noise than an engine of comparable size. Natural gas is expected to be the most common fuel, but landfill gas, or biogas can also be used [1]. The main disadvantages of micro turbines at this stage are its short track record and high costs compared with gas engines.

D. Fuel Cells

Fuel cells are compact, quiet power generators that use hydrogen and oxygen to make electricity. The transportation sector is the major potential market for fuel cells, and car manufacturers are making substantial investments in research and development. Power generation, however, is seen as a market in which fuel cells could be commercialized much more quickly. Fuel cells can convert fuels to electricity at very high efficiencies (35%-60%) [1], compared with conventional technologies. Their efficiency limits the emissions of greenhouse gases. As there is no combustion, other noxious emissions are low.

E. Photovoltaic Systems

Unlike the other DG technologies discussed above, photovoltaic systems are a capital-intensive, renewable technology with very low operating costs. They generate no heat and are inherently small-scale. These characteristics suggest that PV systems are best suited to household or small commercial applications, where power prices on the grid are highest. Operating costs are very low, as there are no fuelling costs. PV systems also are widely used in developing countries, serving rural populations that have no other access to basic energy services. PV systems can be used to provide electricity for a variety of applications in households, community lighting, small businesses, agriculture, healthcare, and water supply the other half of existing PV capacity is on-grid, mostly as distributed generation. Most on-grid PV installations to date have enjoyed very large investment subsidies or favorable prices for the electricity they Generate [1]. The economic viability of PV systems is much higher when they can displace an extension to a distribution line.

F. Wind

Wind generation is rapidly growing in importance as a share of worldwide electricity supply. About 4.2 GW of capacity was installed during the year 2000. Wind power is sometimes considered to be distributed generation, because

the size and location of some wind farms makes it suitable for connection at distribution voltages.

G. Hydro electric resources

Water constantly moves through a vast global cycle, in which it evaporates from oceans, seas and other water reservoirs, forms clouds, precipitates as rain or snow, then flows back to the ocean. The energy of this water cycle, which is driven by the sun, is tapped most efficiently with hydropower.

The principal advantages of using hydropower are:

- Its large renewable domestic resource base.
- The absence of polluting emissions during operation.
- Its capability in some cases to respond quickly to utility load demands.
- Its very low operating costs. Hydroelectric projects also include beneficial effects such as recreation in reservoirs or in tail water below dams.

Disadvantages can include:

- High initial capital cost and
- Potential site-specific and cumulative environmental impacts.

Most of the world’s large hydroelectric potentials have been tapped, but there still remains a large number of small and medium water resources which offer immense power potential at low cost. This vast potential can be effectively tapped using small, mini, micro and pico hydel projects. This option is particularly suited for developing countries like India. The globally accepted classification for hydro is in terms of power output, but the norms vary from country to country. In India, a hydro power plant of capacity lower than 15 MW is termed 'small hydro'. The Central Electricity Authority of India further classifies small hydro schemes as follows :

Size	Unit Size	Installation
Micro	Up to 100 kW	100 kW
Mini	101 – 1000 kW	2000 kW
Small	1001 – 6000 kW	15000 kW

Table 1 – Depending on the capacity

Ultra Low head	Below 3 metres
Medium head	From 30 – 75 metres
High head	Above 75 metres

Table 2 – Depending on the head

IV. ECONOMIC ADVANTAGES OF ON-SITE DISTRIBUTED GENERATION

Distributed generation has some economic advantages over power from the grid, particularly for on-site power production. On-site production avoids transmission and distribution costs, which otherwise amount to about 30% of the cost of delivered electricity. Onsite power production by fossil fuels generates waste heat that can be used by the customer. Distributed generation may also be better positioned to use inexpensive fuels such as landfill gas.

V. GRID BENEFITS OF ON-SITE DISTRIBUTED GENERATION

Distributed generators, depending on location, may offer additional value to the grid:

- Deferral of upgrades to the transmission system. When a transmission system is congested, an appropriately located DG can reduce the congestion and thus can defer the need for an upgrade, particularly when the growth in congestion is low.
- Deferral of upgrades to the distribution system. If a distribution network is operating near capacity or needs to be upgraded to accommodate power flows from the generator, DG installed at a transformer station, may allow a distribution company to cope with the problem, delaying the need to upgrade distribution assets.
- Reduction of losses in the distribution system. On-site generation will cut system losses by reducing power demand on the system. Furthermore, if a distributed generator is located near a large load, then its exported power will also tend to cut system losses. In contrast, power exported to the grid from remote distributed generators may increase these system losses.
- Provision of network support: The connection of distributed generators to networks generally leads to a rise in voltage in the network. In areas where voltage support is difficult, installation of a distributed generator may improve quality of supply.

VI. GRID INTERCONNECTION

Distribution networks traditionally have been designed to take power from high voltage grids and distribute this power to end consumers. The introduction of generating capacity connected to the distribution system need not cause great changes to this system, provided that the capacity does not

actually send power into the network. Once power is sent into the network, the flows of electricity will be changed and even reversed from the normal design. This can lead to a number of technical problems that can affect the stability of the network and quality of electricity supplied. These problems include:

- Voltage control. Electricity sent into the distribution network tends to cause an increase in voltage. This can be beneficial in some instances (e.g. for some rural networks) where operators have problems with low voltages. But in a system operating under normal conditions, these electricity flows can cause difficulties. Difficulties can be alleviated by requiring connection at higher voltage or by upgrading transformers for improved local voltage control. There are related concerns with voltage fluctuations and their potential impact on neighboring consumers.
- Reactive power. Depending on the type of generation, DG can either supply reactive power or will be dependent on it.
- Protection. DG flows can reduce the effectiveness of protection equipment and create operational difficulties under certain conditions. For example, while customers may want the ability to operate in "island" mode (separate from the grid) during a distribution circuit outage, restoring power to them involves important technical and safety considerations [2]. Protection systems are required to ensure that DG systems are not supplying the network during outage conditions and can be resynchronized to the grid when power is restored.

VII. DISTRIBUTED GENERATION IN INDIAN CONTEXT

The main distribution technologies that suits the energy demands of developing countries like India areas follows:

A. Diesel CHP in India

In India, where the power system is heavily reliant on coal, much of it of low quality, and transmission and distribution losses are very high, averaging 22% including "non technical" losses (technical losses alone have been estimated at 13%), compared with an OECD (organization for economic cooperation and development) average of 6.8%. Power reliability problems make distributed power an attractive option for some Indian industries. Industrial power-generating capacity amounts to 15 GW, of which 6 GW is by diesel generation.

B. Small, Mini And Micro Hydel Power

India's hydroelectric potential has been assessed at 84044 MW at 60% load factor of which only 13391.10MW is being utilized (60% l.f) [3]. The estimated utilizable surface water resource is 690 cubic km providing a rich source of hydroelectric development [3]. There are 12 major river basins draining the country all of which when taken together amount to about 25,28,084 sq km of catchment area [3]. Most of these river basin have been exploited for their hydro-electric potential to such an extent that any further efforts may lead to drastic environmental degradation and alter the flow pattern and disturb the delicate network of flora and fauna depending on them (north eastern region of the country is an exception) [4].

Moreover certain other large scale projects which were proposed were turned down either because they were located in areas prone to earthquakes or demanded evacuation of large number of people or would cause huge areas of forest areas to be submerged.

But besides these large river basins there are a number of small and medium river basins comprising west flowing rivers covering the states of Gujarat, maharashtra, karnataka& kerala and east flowing rivers covering orissa, Andhra pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka and Bihar. Not only are the rivers suited for small hydro power plants but the innumerable small stream which feed these rivers are very much suited for mini and micro hydel power project. As these mini and micro project don't require creation of huge reservoirs they can be set up easily within a short period of time and have a short gestation period. Hence these small, mini, and micro power plants are best suited for distributed generation in India.

India has 420 small hydropower projects up to 25 MW station capacity with an aggregate capacity of over 1423 MW. Over 187 projects in this range with aggregate capacity of 521 MW are under construction [5] An estimated potential of about 15,000 MW of small hydropower projects exists in India. Ministry of Non-conventional Energy Sources has created a database of potential sites of small hydro and 4096 potential sites with an aggregate capacity of 10,071 MW for projects up to 25 MW capacity have been identified. 13 States in India namely, Himachal Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, Punjab, Haryana, Madhya Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Orissa, West Bengal, Maharashtra and Rajasthan have announced policies for setting up commercial SHP projects through private sector participation.

C. Pico-hydro projects

PICO HYDRO projects are hydroelectric projects with a power generation capacity of up to 10 KW which convert energy in water flowing down a gradient into electrical energy. It comprises of tapping water from a natural stream flowing down from a gradient at higher elevation, passing

through a water conducting system and letting into a turbine which drives an electrical generator to produce electricity.

These projects are particularly suited for small scale industries located in rural areas and also for community electrification of remote villages. Pico hydro systems require only small water flows and therefore there are many sites at which they can be used. They are onsite DG units and are not designed to supply surplus power to the grid. Even in countries with extensive grid electrification, small communities are often not connected because of the high costs of step-down transformers and low revenues. Locally manufactured systems can be produced which have much lower long term costs per kilowatt than solar, wind and diesel systems. The market for pico hydro in India is largely unexploited due to a number of inhibiting factors:

- Pico hydro technology is not available in many countries.
- Where pico hydro equipment is available it is generally too expensive or of dubious reliability.
- Potential customers lack information on how to generate income from pico hydropower.

A typical 200w pico hydro turbine is shown in figure 3, which has a propeller and an alternator mounting at the same frame. Most pico hydro generators are equipped with electronic load controller (ELC) helps in overcoming fluctuation in voltage and frequency and thus ensures power quality.

Figure 3

VIII. MERITS OF SMALL, MINI, MICRO AND PICO-HP OVER LARGE SCALE HYDEL POWER PLANTS

The biggest advantage of SHP (small hydro power) is that it is the only 'clean' and renewable source of energy available round the clock. It is free from many issues and controversies that continue to 'hound' large hydro projects, like the:

- submergence of forests
- siltation of reservoirs
- rehabilitation and relocation
- and seismological threats

Other benefits of small hydro are

- user-friendliness
- low cost
- short gestation period

IX. WHAT IS BEST FOR INDIA

Most of the DG technologies used in developed countries have little relevance in the Indian context.

- The cost per unit kWh is high for IC engines and gas turbines.
- Sites suitable for wind, tidal and wave energy power generation are few in number.
- The photovoltaic technology, till date, is extremely costly because of huge capital required
- Moreover growing concern about the environment and stringent emission norms make generation of power from fossil fuel DC technology economically unviable. Taking the above mentioned facts, the huge hydroelectric potential of India, and the controversies surrounding large hydel projects into account, it can be seen that small, mini, micro and pico hydel generation is best suited for India.

X. SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC IMPLICATIONS

The social impact of wide deployment of small, mini, micro and pico hydro power generation for DG in India is discussed in detail below:

A. Impact on rural communities.

- It serves to enhance economic development and living standards especially in remote areas with little or no electricity.
- In some cases, rural dwellers can switch over from firewood cooking to electricity thus limiting their exposure to the noxious fumes.
- On the macro level, rural communities have been able to attract new industries - mostly related to agriculture - owing to their ability to draw power at

low cost from SHP stations. This leads to greater employment generation.

- It will help the government in achieving the rural electrification target at a faster rate and at minimal cost.
- Community projects will create a sense of social belongingness among people.
- It will help increase the percapita income of rural communities as they can sell the surplus power to the grid.

B. Decentralisation of power

SHPs when implemented by the local bodies such as panchayats will serve to make them economically more self sufficient through sale of surplus power. Thus by strengthening the hand of local bodies rapid progress of remote areas through decentralization process becomes easily achievable.

C. Benefits to society as a whole

- Consumers will get power at lower tariff as more power becomes available at lower per unit cost.
- Consumers will be relieved from frequent power cuts and load shedding.
- Consumers will immensely benefit from better regulation and power quality.
- As on-site DG eliminates need for costly high voltage transmission lines and large distribution lines. The problem of land acquisition for their construction and the related woes of people can be done away with.
- The effect of high voltage transmission lines on the health of the people living near it is and the interferences created by them on radio and TV signals are done away with.
- More employment opportunities both at plant management level and in the manufacturing sector for related machinery will improve living standards of the people.
- Availability of power at low cost will attract more investments, which would be more evenly distributed throughout the country rather than being limited to cities alone.
- As percapita power consumption increases the living standards of people will improve.
- Increased use of power will increase the demand for more electrical goods and this will lead to a spur in growth in the industrial sector.

D. Impact On Environment

SHP doesn't require forest area to be submerged, as huge reservoirs are not required. Moreover they are free from emissions. So they are environment friendly.

E. Promotion of tourism

The small reservoirs created for SHP's serve to enhance the beauty of the landscape and thus improve the tourism potential of the region.

F. Agriculture and irrigation

The reservoirs created for SHP may also serve the purpose of irrigation during drought and act as safe guard for the farming society.

G. Rise in ground water table

The presence of small reservoir increase the percolation of ground water and thus enhance the supply of drinking water.

XI. CASE STUDIES

Small hydro power plants in operation in India

1. The Indushree Power Project in Raskat, Himachal Pradesh

Raskat, in Himachal Pradesh, is a typical 'remote Indian village in the hills'-lush green, small, with no more than 15 homesteads accommodating a small populace of 100, and frugal in basic facilities. Since August 2002, it has been the source of reliable and quality electric power supply to the inhabitants of a dozen adjoining villages. With support from the MNES (Ministry of Non-Conventional Energy Sources), the UNDP (United Nations Development Programme), and GEF (Global Environment Facility), a micro hydel power project, based on the Raskat Nallah was commissioned here in August 2002.

This 1 MW small hydel resources initiative has brought light, and hope, to nearly 700 homes in 12 remote, inaccessible villages in and beyond Raskat. The powerhouse has lit up Pulga, Kalga, Barshani, Tosh, and Sheela-villages located in the upper reaches of the Parvati valley, connected to the mainland with no more than a fairweather pony track. Thanks to round-the-clock electricity, villages all the way up to Nakthan, some 20 km by foot from Raskat, are gradually waking to a new dawn.

Beneath the village serendipity, the social and economic benefits of clean and reliable power supply from the Indushree Power Project, the micro hydel power station in Raskat, are already in evidence. Reminisces Maney Chand Verma, 32, a local villager in-charge of on-site plant maintenance. Till only last year, my two daughters had a hard time preparing for their school examinations, with only a kerosene lamp for light. Now, they study well into

midnight even as their mother keeps them company while spinning yarn on her small loom.' He goes on, 'Earlier when light would come from the Bhuntar grid, our televisions would never work even with the stabilizers synchronized to maximum voltage.'

Mohinder Kumar, 21, is a helper at the reservoir site of the Raskat powerhouse. He earns Rs 2500 a month. That's handsome earning in the countryside for someone with modest education.

The village power plant employs nine other persons, including four technicians/engineers, a manager for operations and electrical maintenance, an assistant manager for civil works, and three helpers like Mohinder. Bhardwaj has made sure that each member of his staff is a local.

The Indushree Power Project in Raskat, Himachal Pradesh, one of the north Indian mountain states, is one of the 20 demonstration projects being supported in the hilly states of India under the \$7.5 million MNES/UNDP/GEF initiative on Optimizing Development of Small Hydel Resources. The project seeks to popularize the use of small hydro energy resources to address the issue of protecting biodiversity and global warming. The overarching objective is to upgrade the institutional and human resource capabilities at the local and national levels, with a view to facilitating the formulation of a national strategy and master plan in this sector. To date, master and zonal plans have been formulated in 13 hilly states of India and over 2000 sites have been identified for small hydel development.

The 24-hour assured power supply has created earning opportunities for other enterprising villagers as well. More than 40 electric ropeway trolleys have come up within the 20-kilometre radius of the Raskat micro hydel project. These ropeways, put up at a unit cost of Rs 1 00 000 carry general supplies, farm consignments, and other goods from and to the Raskat market for the villagers from their homes atop the hills. The savings for the villagers in time and effort have been enormous, making the ropeway trolley business a runaway success.

Not a single tree was cut while putting up the project. Indeed, to keep the frequent landslides from damaging the project site, thousands of trees have been planted on the loose rocky terrain around the site.

Projects under construction

PICO Hydro Projects in Karnataka Technology Informatics Design Endeavour (TIDE), a voluntary organisation specialised in technical support has taken up an eco-friendly project that addresses this issue by demonstrating a decentralized Pico-Hydro power project for meeting the energy needs of small communities in the hilly areas of Karnataka. The major thrust of the project is on

demonstrating technical, managerial and economic feasibility of diffusing this technology for community use and its positive impact on environment by reducing carbon emission, deforestation and soil erosion. The project has a strong component of community participation, which will raise a contribution upto 40 percent of the total budget. The project has been undertaken with the assistance of the Norwegian government with a total support of Rs.368 lakhs. The project has been undertaken in remote areas for the benefit of the poor and marginalized. Additionally, the following factors are significant: § Implemented by local NGO with technical support from TIDE § Setting up of a community oriented project § Post project operation and maintenance by local committees Work of erection of the main equipment on four out of the seven sites is nearing completion. On completion, the project will provide uninterrupted and reliable electrical power for domestic as well as commercial use without any recurring fuel costs and very little maintenance cost. More importantly, it would create a replicable model for the small communities in the hilly areas devoid of electricity to become self-sufficient by having an access to an independent power generation project of their own.

Figure 4

XII IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS OF A PICO PROJECT

Nepal case study

This describes the process from site selection to installation and commissioning of a pico hydro scheme at Kushadevi, a small community close to Kathmandu. [8]

Potential and demand

An initial estimate of the hydro resource was made in order to determine whether there was sufficient potential. The site was visited at the end of the dry season enabling the

minimum flow to be estimated. This was found to be approximately 10 l/s. The available head was in excess of 100 metres, and therefore ideal for a Pelton turbine. Assuming an overall efficiency of 50%, there was sufficient year round potential to generate in excess of 5 kW.

There are 88 households within approximately 1 kilometre of the likely location of the power house. The principal demand was for lighting and radios. There was also interest in having a grain mill .

Survey

Having established that a 4.4kW scheme design was required, a detailed site survey was carried out. The flow was measured at the end of what happened to be a particularly long dry season and the flow was found to be 9 l/s. Since this was a worst case flow, that should only occur in exceptional years, it was decided that a design flow of up to 13.5 l/s could be used, provided that a smaller turbine nozzle suitable for 9 l/s was supplied that could be fitted at very dry times.

A plan of the village was drawn, showing all the houses and the stream, in order to determine the best location for the powerhouse. The highest position for the intake was found to be an accessible point just below where a number of small water sources combined. Since the stream flowed through a steep sided valley there were only a few accessible places where a powerhouse could be located above the flood level of the stream. One location had the advantage of being very well positioned for electricity distribution (see plan) and provided a gross head of 80 metres with respect to the highest position for the intake, as measured using an Abney level. The next suitable site was much further down stream and would have resulted in a considerably more expensive penstock and a longer and more costly distribution system.

Penstock

Since a canal was not a viable option, a long penstock was required. High Density PolyEthylene (HDPE) pipe was chosen as the penstock material as it is cheaper than PVC pipe in Nepal, is flexible, smooth walled, strong and does not degrade in sunlight. The total length required was estimated to be 400m, though at installation it was found that an additional 30m was required. The pipes were buried section. However, this would have increased the total head loss to over 12m and was therefore not implemented. Intake/Forebay The intake and forebay were combined in this project, as the soil and topography made the construction of a long canal un realistic, especially as there was no surplus flow to allow for seepage losses.

Powerhouse

The Powerhouse was constructed using locally available mud, stone and wood. The stone and mud was used to make the walls which were approximately 0.5 metres thick and the wood was used for the door and two windows and to support the roof. The roof was made from corrugated galvanised iron sheet, pitched at approximately 30 degrees to ensure that water does not collect on it. The internal dimensions were 4.8 x 2.7 metres to provide sufficient room for milling as well as for the turbine, generator and control equipment.

Turbine and generator

The induction motor is driven at approximately 5% above its synchronous speed in order to function as a generator. The speeds required to generate 50 Hz from 2 pole, 4 pole and 6 pole induction machines are shown in Table 5.

Number of Poles	Shaft speed (RPM)	Diameter of runner (m)	Max flow rate (1/S)
2	3150	0.10	3.6
4	1575	0.20	14.2
6	1050	0.30	32.0

Table 5

Controller

A locally manufactured 5 kW Induction Generator Controller (IGC) was used to directly regulate the voltage of the generator and to indirectly control the frequency and shaft speed. Two Pico IGC boards were used in parallel as each board only has a capacity of 3 kW.

XII. ON-SITE DISTRIBUTED GENERATION VERSUS CENTRAL POWER

A. Advantages:

- On-site power production circumvents transmission and distribution costs for the delivery of electricity. These costs average about 30% of the total cost of electricity.
- Distributed generation has other economic advantages for particular customers. For example, customers with sizeable heat loads may produce both heat and power economically. Some customers have access to low cost fuel (such as landfill gas or local biomass), compared with commercially delivered fuel.
- Distributed generation can also encourage greater competition in electricity supply, allowing even customers without DG greater choice in suppliers.

B. Disadvantages

On the other hand, small-scale generation has a few direct cost disadvantages over central generation.

- There is a more limited selection of fuels and technologies to generate electricity - oil, natural gas, or photovoltaic systems, and, in certain cases, biomass or waste fuels.
- The smaller generators used in DG cost more per kilowatt to build than larger plants used in central generation.
- The smaller plants used in DG operate at lower fuel-conversion efficiencies than those of larger plants of the same type used in central generation.

The above mentioned disadvantages exist for techniques of Dg other than shps' and mini and micro hydel DG's . The main disadvantage of hydel DG is that I cannot be implemented anywhere . it can be created only in hilly areas where water having head is present. Apart from this it suffers from no other major disadvantages except the fact that the electronic load control system used in pico hydro power is not available in most developing countries and needs to be imported.

XIII. CONCLUSION

Thus we have seen that though distributed generation has a number of advantages over conventional central power generation, and is most suitable for tapping small power resources scattered over a large area, yet it still can't replace the grid. Grid based central power system is still preferred for most of the cases except in situations when the cost of installation of transmission system is too high. Thus an ideal power system, which has the benefits of DG as well as grid, can be formulated by accommodating these DGs into the grid along with central power units so that surplus power generated at DGs can be easily sent to regions, which have a deficit.

In the Indian context, distributed generation through small , mini ,micro and pico hydel projects do hold the solution to power crisis . Moreover distributed generation also aids in promoting economic development and social welfare . moreover community distribution projects by ensuring greater participation of people helps to create a civic conscience in the society.

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